

Synthesis, characterization and crystal structure of a square-planar copper(II) Schiff base complex

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Abstract : The synthesis and characterization of a copper(II) complex of 1,3-bis(5-nitrosalicylideneamino)-2-propanol, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7)$ is described. The complex has been characterized by elemental analysis, IR and X-ray crystallography. The molecule adopts a square-planar geometry and displays significant twists from coplanarity of its nitro groups, aromatic rings and methylene groups of the amine segment.

Keywords : Square-planar Cu^{II} , 1,3-bis(5-nitrosalicylideneamino)-2-propanol, X-ray crystal structure, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

Metal complexes containing Schiff base ligands have been of great interest even after over a hundred years of study¹⁻⁴. Schiff bases are capable to form chelates with a considerable number of metal ions and are in demand because they are straightforward in preparation and are moderate electron donors with easily-tunable electronic as well as steric effects thus being versatile^{5,6}. Schiff base metal complexes play a crucial role in the development of coordination chemistry related to catalysis and enzymatic processes, magnetism and molecular architectures.

The coordination chemistry of copper complexes has been the focus of numerous studies since it may provide important clues for better understanding the structures and probable mechanisms of reactions involving copper-containing metalloproteins⁷. The structures of copper complexes are affected by a number of factors such as the ligand field stabilization energies, Jahn-Teller distortion, counter-ion effects, steric effects etc. The salen ligands with four coordinating sites are found to be efficient Schiff bases that may bind the copper(II) center with the favorable square-planar geometry. The chemistry of copper(II) com-

plexes with salen ligands has been extensively investigated in order to explore different catalytic reactions.

Herein a report has been made regarding the synthesis, characterization and X-ray crystal structure of a square-planar Cu^{II} complex with 1,3-bis(5-nitrosalicylideneamino)-2-propanol.

Results and discussion

IR spectra :

In the IR spectrum of the compound (Fig. 1) the strong band at 1646 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\text{C}=\text{N}$ which suggests coordination of the Schiff base ligand to the metal center through the imine nitrogen atoms. The broad band at 3330 cm^{-1} is indicative of the presence of aliphatic O-H group.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectrum of the free ligand 1,3-bis(5-nitrosalicylideneamino)-2-propanol in dichloromethane solution features one highly intense band at 218 nm, assigned to intraligand $\pi\rightarrow\pi^*$ transition primarily based on aromatic salicyl moieties. Appearance of one peak suggests equivalent nature of the two salicyl groups due mainly to the conforma-

tional non-rigid nature of the substituted trimethylene spacer allowing to restore the molecular symmetry of the whole ligand in solution. The $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition pertinent to azomethine ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) function also appeared at 237 nm but the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition related to phenolic motif did not appear. There is no significant shifting of peak positions on increasing the solvent polarity.

The electronic spectrum of the complex (Fig. 1) in weakly polar noncoordinating dichloromethane solvent shows two ligand-centered major absorption peaks at 219 and 248 nm. The first transition is assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ ILCT. This band remains almost unaffected by metal coordination and imprinted almost at the same wavelength encountered for the ligand. The $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition corresponding to the azomethine fragment underwent a red shift by *ca.* 10 nm on going from ligand to complex, consistent with azomethine nitrogen chelation to bivalent copper. $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{ligand}$ charge transfer (MLCT) transition appears in near UV region at 365 nm. Three spin allowed ligand field

transitions viz. ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ are expected for square-planar complexes to appear at high energy and often difficult to identify being overlaid by strong ILCT and MLCT bands. Hence, it is logical to assume that the MLCT band encroaching to visible region imparts color to the square-planar complex. Aiming to investigate the effect of polarity and coordination ability of the solvent on the structure of the title complex, efforts were made to record the absorption spectra in acetonitrile and DMSO medium. The high-energy spectral characteristics remain unaltered except with the generation of weak, broad absorption peak near 610 nm, attributed to d-d transition (${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$) in a distorted octahedral geometry (O_h) resulted from the binding of solvent molecules along the axial direction of the square-planar complex (D_{2h}). 2E_g and ${}^2T_{2g}$ terms of the octahedral Cu^{II} ion ($3d^9$) split under the influence of the tetragonal distortion giving rise to three spin allowed transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$. Often the three bands are not resolved in practice since the four

Fig. 1. IR and electronic spectra of the compound.

lower orbitals (d_{xz} , d_{yz} , d_{xy} , d_{z^2}) are so close in energy that electron transfer from these individual orbitals to the upper $d_{x^2-y^2}$ level cannot be distinguished, instead overlap and appear in the form of one broad band as observed in this case.

Electrochemical studies :

The cyclic voltammetry of the complex (Fig. 2) displays less pronounced irreversible anodic oxidation waves at $E_{pa} = 1.02$ and 1.36 V. The signal at low positive potential has been assigned to metal oxidation relevant to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ couple and the higher potential shoulder is believed to be associated with ligand centered phenolate/phenoxy radical oxidation process, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{L}] \rightarrow [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}^{\bullet})]^+$. The ligand-centered oxidation has become more difficult to accomplish in the complex as evident from the enhanced oxidation potential by a margin of *ca.* 0.3 V relative to the free state (H_2L) is in accord with the electron deficient nature of the coordinated ligand. The cathodic scan attests one reversible wave ($E_{1/2} = -0.15$ V, $E_{pc} = -0.19$ V and $E_{pa} = -0.11$ V, $\Delta E_p = 80$ mV) and an

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of the compound.

irreversible peak at -0.77 V corresponding to the metal centered reductions pertinent to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}/\text{Cu}^0$ couples, respectively. The ligand reduction primarily localized on azomethine linkage in the complex has been shifted to more negative potential compared to the free ligand and appeared at -1.09 V as a broad irreversible response.

X-Ray crystallography :

Fig. 3 shows an ORTEP drawing of the title complex and Table 1 lists the distances and angles involving the copper atom. The Cu atom has a distorted square-planar coordination with bond angles indicating relatively slight distortions with four angles in the range 89.13 – 91.72° and two angles being the same of 168.86° . The Cu-O and Cu-N bond lengths are found to be 1.930 and 1.952 Å, respectively. These distances fall within the range of those of previously reported related compounds^{8–11}. The C7-N1 and C7_a-N1_a distance of the imine fragment of the complex are the same and has been found to be $1.277(4)$

Fig. 3. ORTEP diagram of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7)$. Thermal ellipsoids are at 40% probability level. All hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Table 1. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles ($^\circ$) for the complex

Bond lengths (Å)			
Cu1-N1	1.952(2)	O1-C1	1.293(3)
Cu1-O1	1.930(2)	N1-C7	1.277(4)
Bond angles ($^\circ$)			
O1-Cu1-N1	91.72(8)	O1_a-Cu1-N1_a	91.72(8)
O1-Cu1-O1_a	89.13(8)	N1-Cu1-N1_a	89.59(9)
O1-Cu1-N1_a	168.86(9)	Cu1-O1-C1	126.29(15)
O1_a-Cu1-N1	168.86(9)	Cu1-N1-C7	125.66(17)

Å while that of the free ligand have been reported as 1.292(4) and 1.284(4) Å¹². This shortening in length of the azomethine moiety in the free ligand possibly stems from the different electronic nature of H⁺ and Cu²⁺. Being very hard and strongly Lewis acidic in nature, H⁺ is capable to withdraw electron density from the imine moiety of the free ligand while the soft Cu^{II} center could not withdraw as much electron density unlike H⁺, thereby accounting for the discernible reduction in the C=N bond length of the complex. The molecule adopts a distorted square-planar geometry where the N and O atoms are deviated from the mean plane constructed by Cu1-O1-O1_a-N1-N1_a at a distance of ±0.187 Å and ±0.190 Å, respectively. The dihedral angle between this mean plane and the phenyl ring is found to be 19.89°. There are significant twists from coplanarity of this molecule, for the two approximate planes, the C8-N1-C7-C6-C5-C4-N2-O4-O3-C3-C2-C1-O1 and its counterpart opposite to the copper center are folded at the C9 atom making a dihedral angle of 16.26°. Comparing this value with the free ligand (11.21°)¹² it can be concluded that the ligand has been puckered to a considerable extent upon binding to the metal.

Experimental

General :

5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde and 1,3-diamino-2-propanol of AR grade were purchased from Aldrich and used as received. Copper(II) perchlorate was prepared by the reaction of Cu₂(OH)₂CO₃ with perchloric acid in water. Methanol was of reagent grade and used without further purification. Doubled distilled water was used throughout. Microanalysis (CHN) was performed in a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. FT-IR spectra were obtained on a Nicolet MAGNA-IR 750 spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ region. UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Hitachi Model U-4001 spectrophotometer. Cyclic voltammetry (at room temperature in the potential range from -2.0 V to +1.80 V with a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹) was performed at a platinum

electrode vs SCE in acetonitrile solution containing TEAP as the supporting electrolyte using an EG&G PARC electrochemical analysis system (Model 250/5/0).

Preparation of 1,3-bis(5-nitrosalicylideneamino)-2-propanol :

The ligand was prepared following the method of Miukuriya¹². Thus, a solution of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde dissolved in 25 ml of methanol was mixed with 1,3-diamino-2-propanol in 2 : 1 molar ratio. Upon stirring for 30 min, the ligand was precipitated as a yellow mass. It was filtered off, washed with methanol and used for the synthesis of the complex.

Synthesis of Cu^{II}(C₁₇H₁₃N₄O₇) :

A solution of 1,3-bis(5-nitrosalicylideneamino)-2-propanol (0.194 g, 0.5 mmol) in 20 ml of methanol was added to an aqueous solution (10 ml) of copper(II) perchlorate (0.185 g, 0.5 mmol) with constant stirring. The mixture was stirred for 10 min and then filtered off. Dark green crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained after 3 days. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃N₄O₇Cu (%) : C, 45.45; H, 2.89; N, 12.47. Found : C, 45.42; H, 2.83; N, 12.44. Characteristic IR data (cm⁻¹) : 1646 (s, ν_{C=N}), 3330 (s, ν_{O-H}), 1604 (s, ν_{C-O}/phenolate), 866 (w, ν_{C-NO₂}).

Crystal structure determination and structural refinement of the compound :

The diffraction data were collected at 150 K on a Bruker Smart Apex CCD diffractometer using monochromated Mo-Kα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). Data reduction and cell refinement were performed using the programs Bruker SAINT and Bruker SMART. An empirical absorption correction by using the SADABS¹³ program was applied which resulted in transmission coefficients ranging from 0.645 to 0.960. The structure was solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least-squares based on F² with anisotropic thermal parameters for non-hydrogen atoms using SHELXS-97¹⁴ (structure solution) and SHELXL-97¹⁵ (structure refinement). The soft-

Table 2. Crystal data for the complex

Formula	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₇ Cu
Formula weight	448.86
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c (No. 15)
<i>a</i> (Å)	22.046(12)
<i>b</i> (Å)	10.853(6)
<i>c</i> (Å)	7.105(4)
β (°)	101.988(9)
V (Å ³)	1662.9(16)
Z	4
D _{Calcd.} (g/cm ³)	1.793
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.369
F(000)	912
Temperature (K)	150
λ (Å)	0.71073 (Mo-Kα)
θ Min-Max (°)	1.9–27.0
Reflections collected	3950
Independent reflections	1769
Observed data [I > 2σ(I)]	1459
Data/restraints/parameters	1769/0/140
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.044
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R1 = 0.0397 wR2 = 0.0914
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.0521 wR2 = 0.0958

ware used for computing molecular graphics was ORTEP3 for Windows V 1.08. The crystallographic data are summarized in Table 2.

Supporting information

CCDC 1484928 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be

obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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